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Preamble

This report constitutes the first part of Deliverable D.3.3., the aim of which is to provide lessons for understanding the barriers and levers to the implementation of excreta source separation projects, focusing specifically on the acceptance of the stakeholders involved, not only the users of these buildings, but also all the stakeholders involved in the day-to-day management of the buildings providing this separation (installation, cleaning, maintenance). This work is based on an analysis of current urine source separation projects in the Ile-de-France region identified and/or studied by the OCAPI programme, and on the implementation and operation of a demonstrator dedicated to this topic at the Ecole des Ponts, in the Coriolis building. As the design of this demonstrator required more time than initially planned (see explanations below), it was decided to deliver deliverable D.3.3. in two stages. This version (intermediate D.3.3) includes the progress made in defining the demonstrator up to 10 July 2025. It does not include the analysis of the appropriation of the demonstrator by the stakeholders (users and personnel in charge of its operation), which will only take place once the demonstrator has been completed.

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1 Executive summary

This interim report, produced as part of the Horizon Europe P2GreenN project under Work Package 3 (“Supporting the Transition”), focuses on the social acceptability of source-separating sanitation systems in the Paris Region. It is embedded in Task 3.3, which investigates how various stakeholders—including citizens, farmers, and end-users—perceive the circular reuse of nutrients from human excreta in agriculture. The central objective is to assess public acceptance of these systems and identify the enabling or limiting conditions for their broader deployment.

The report is divided into two main sections. The first section deals with the acceptabilities of the users of diverting toilets in different projects mainly located in the Great Paris. This topic is analysed through two sub-sections.

The first one presents a set of field surveys carried out between 2016 and 2024 in varied contexts such as festivals, university campuses, temporary urban planning sites, and an upcoming eco-district. Across these diverse settings, the studies reveal a generally positive attitude toward separating toilets, especially when their design is close to conventional models and when their usage is intuitive. At the École des Ponts, a dry urinal was installed during a public event and proved effective and acceptable; the majority of users did not even notice it was waterless, and over 90% of respondents supported the idea of using urine as fertiliser. Nevertheless, most participants had limited knowledge about the fate of excreta and the broader environmental implications of sanitation systems. At the Garorock music festival, vacuum-based urine-diverting toilets were installed and tested in a high-volume setting. Despite low initial awareness, users quickly adapted and offered favourable feedback, although some reluctance emerged regarding the adoption of such systems in private homes, particularly among older users. In the semi-public setting of Cité Fertile, dry toilets with a conveyor-belt mechanism were well received, highlighting how user-friendly design and discrete operation foster acceptance. These toilets were perceived as environmentally responsible and, for some, even enhanced the venue’s image. However, a lack of public understanding of how sanitation systems work and where waste ends up remained a recurring theme. A forward-looking survey among future residents of the Saint-Vincent-de-Paul eco-district in Paris provided further insights. The households surveyed were generally supportive of urine-diverting toilets, viewing them as consistent with their environmental values. Many respondents, however, were unaware of technical constraints such as the incompatibility of certain cleaning products with urine recovery systems. The survey underscored the need for user education and tailored support to facilitate behavioural adaptation. Demonstrations, workshops, signage, and printed guides were identified as particularly useful tools. Notably, male respondents generally did not resist the recommendation to urinate sitting down, a key behavioural requirement for effective urine separation.

The second sub-section analyses case studies involving the operational sustainability of separating toilets in public or semi-public spaces. It shows that the long-term success of such systems relies heavily on day-to-day maintenance and the organisational structure

supporting them. Projects like Sud-Fleuri and Parcelle Y experienced premature termination due to insufficient institutional backing, unclear responsibilities, and inadequate maintenance routines. In contrast, Cité Fertile's long-standing success illustrates the importance of having a dedicated team, a well-defined management structure, and an ability to perform frequent, small technical adjustments. Maintenance is not merely a technical issue but intersects with social and institutional dimensions. Its visibility and quality strongly influence user perception and, by extension, system acceptance.

In the second section, the report introduces the Azuris demonstrator, an evolving pilot project at the École des Ponts, which began in 2016 with the simple collection of urine from a dry urinal and storage in the basement. This initiative is now being expanded under the P2Green project into a multi-faceted demonstrator that includes new toilet technologies, treatment systems like FreezePee, and a dedicated technical room. The demonstrator will serve both as a research platform and an educational tool, aiming to evaluate system efficiency, user behaviour, and institutional integration. It is being developed with the input of researchers, designers, administrative staff, and P2Green consortium partners to ensure both usability and scalability.

In conclusion, the findings show that technical feasibility is only one part of the equation. The success and acceptability of source-separating sanitation systems are deeply intertwined with factors such as maintenance quality, public understanding, institutional commitment, and user engagement. Acceptance increases when systems are clean, reliable, and perceived as environmentally meaningful. However, their long-term viability depends on the invisible but essential labour of maintenance, institutional clarity, and educational outreach. The Paris Region case offers valuable lessons for scaling such systems in other European contexts and integrating them into broader sustainability transitions.

2 Introduction

This report is part of [P2GreenN projet](#). P2GreenN is aimed at fostering a paradigm shift, from a linearly organised resource and nutrient system within the agri-food supply chain, towards a circular material flow system between urban and rural areas thereby restoring the coupling of the water-agri-food system using a holistic symbiotic resource management approach following the 3R principle “Reduce, Reuse, Recover”. P2GreenN develops new circular governance solutions for the transition from fork to farm to halt and eliminate N & P pollution by connecting blue urban with green rural infrastructure, focussing on circular nutrient flows of nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P). This will be done through implementation and demonstration of innovative N & P recovery solutions for the utilisation of human excreta from urban settlements and its conversion into safe bio-based fertilisers for agricultural production in three pilot regions (Baltic Sea region, North German Plain, Axarquía in Southern Spain). This approach will be extended to follower regions in Italy, France, Greece and Hungary. P2GreenN will further enable policy makers to replicate this model in all regional settings across Europe. To facilitate systemic change, co-creation strategies will be key, including the participation of all relevant stakeholders and harmonised innovation governance frameworks.

This document is part of Work Package 3, called “Supporting the transition”. WP3 will support the circular transition in the pilot regions as well as safeguard the scale-up potential to the follower regions and for the EU-level by a) developing circular business models, b) exploring societal acceptance, c) proposing urban planning pathways, and d) developing a proposal for a legislative framework. More precisely, this work is included in the task 3.3 (“Awareness raising & enhancing social acceptance”) which aims to reveal how the different actors in the “P2GreenN chain” – i.e. local citizens, farmers, other N & P stakeholders, everyday people who buy the agri-end-product – can accept this new circular solution that tries to close the loop in an innovative way, using the human sanitary waste to fertilise the field where their food is produced.

Task 3.3 comprises of several deliverables, including D3.3. (“Lessons learned and recommendations on action for user acceptance”), produced by the LEESU OCAPÍ team. This deliverable provides lessons for understanding the stakes and barriers specifically related to user acceptance in order to foster a broader awareness rising and societal acceptance. In this report, the term “users” refers to those who use diverting toilets, but the scope of the analysis has been broadened to include those responsible for operating the buildings that house these facilities. Indeed, it appears that user acceptance is closely linked to the ability of these latter actors to keep the facilities clean and functional over time. The observations and findings are drawn from ongoing projects with several experimental installations of source separation of urine in the Ile-de-France region.

The deliverable is organised into two parts. The first part (section 2 of the document) identifies factors influencing toilet user acceptance based on fieldwork conducted primarily in the Paris region and observed by the OCAPÍ programme: these elements are derived

from surveys conducted directly with users (section 2.1) and from the analysis of detailed case studies in areas where separate toilets have been installed (section 2.2).

The second part (section 3 of this report) deals with the implementation and observation of the functioning of a demonstration model of separation at source within the Coriolis building at the École des Ponts in Marne la Vallée. In this interim version, only the implementation part is covered, that means from the beginning of the project until the 10th of July 2025.

3 Analysis of user acceptability in the Paris region

For more than a decade, source separation of human excreta has been developed in urban projects in France, particularly in the Ile-de-France region. These projects vary in scope (ranging from isolated trials to entire neighborhoods), setting (individual homes, collective housing, offices, event venues, public buildings), waste type (urine only, feces only, or both urine and feces), and stakeholders (individuals, private entities, local authorities, or research initiatives)¹.

Since its establishment in 2015, the OCAPI program has conducted analyses and taken action on the dynamics of the emergence and deployment of source separation of excreta, mainly (but not exclusively) in the Paris region, in order to understand the driving forces behind it and even support the success of some projects. The approaches adopted and the disciplines involved are diverse, as shown in the presentation of the program's seven areas of focus (Figure 1).

Figure 1: OCAPI program themes

Diagram legend

- DEMO: Demonstration
- ANIM°: Animation
- SOCIO: Sociological issues
- PROCEDES: Process
- AGRO: Agronomical issues
- SANTE: Health issues
- METABO: Urban metabolism

¹ As part of the “Fertile Toilets” project, carried out in collaboration with the Paris Region Institute, OCAPI has developed a web page presenting all the projects identified up to March 2024. See <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/495f0ceb57044510b121d2f144e8acbd>.

The issue of user acceptability is addressed in the following two thematic areas: the “socio” area and the “demo” area. In practice, this translates into three types of action:

- monitoring experiments in which the OCAPI program has been involved or has initiated: these include the projects mentioned in section 2.2 of this report, as well as the installation of a demonstration system for source separation in the Coriolis building of the École des Ponts et Chaussées in Champs-sur-Marne (mentioned in part 3).
- analysis of operations carried out by institutional actors (companies, associations, local authorities), such as the Saint-Vincent de Paul project currently under construction²;
- and, finally, questionnaire surveys of the public or users carried out as part of research projects related to the innovations and experiments mentioned above (discussed in section 2.1).

3.1 Surveys of toilet users

The OCAPI team has carried out a number of surveys of source-separating toilet users as part of various research projects. They targeted different audiences and contexts (festivals, transitional urban planning experiments and future urban projects), followed specific objectives and protocols each time, and focused on different models of source-separating toilet (waterless urinals, dry toilets, water-based source-separating toilets, vacuum-operated source-separating toilets). The surveys were carried out between 2016 and 2024, making it possible to assess changes in the general public's perception of these alternative approaches to toilets and their awareness of the associated issues.

3.1.1 The D.Event survey at Ecole des Ponts

The survey concerns the use of a dry urinal (with urine stored underground³) located near a university lecture theatre during an event attended by several hundred people in July 2016.

Background and objectives of the survey

Quite soon after the start of the OCAPI research programme in 2015, its leader, Fabien Esculier, felt it was important to have an initial experimental source separation system at Ecole des Ponts. This gave rise to the Azuris pilot project (presented in more detail in part 3). In practice, this involved diverting urine from a waterless urinal located in the toilet block on the ground floor of the school's Coriolis building and storing it in a tank in the basement.

² Saint-Vincent de Paul project is an eco-neighbourhood in Paris, built on a former hospital site, where it has been decided to implement an ambitious scheme for the separate collection of urine and its *on-site* conversion into fertiliser. This is the biggest operation of its kind in France.

³ A technical presentation of this device is provided in part 3.

The system was commissioned on 23 June 2016, to coincide with an international conference on Design Thinking⁴, which was attended by over 300 people. The conference took place in the Carnot amphitheatre on the ground floor of the Coriolis building, just opposite the toilets where the OCAPI dry urinal was located. The members of the OCAPI team involved in the Azuris project took the opportunity to: raise awareness of the principle of selective urine collection, present the OCAPI project via a stand located in the hall between the amphitheatre and the toilets (Figure 2) and, conduct a questionnaire survey among the event's participants.

Figure 1: OCAPI stand at the D.event 2016

The survey consisted of around twenty questions with the aim of finding out (a) the perceptions of individuals who had used the dry urinal (this part only concerned the men who had used them) (b) their knowledge of the use of wastewater sludge in agriculture (c) their opinion on the prospect of consuming products fertilised by urine. The questionnaires were distributed in paper form and filled in directly during breaks in the conference: they were addressed primarily to men leaving the toilets, but also to all people (women and men) who had stopped at the OCAPI stand.

Main findings

Around one hundred questionnaires were distributed and 87 were collected (some were only partially completed). Two-thirds of the questionnaires were completed by men, which is not surprising given the protocol used distribution was focused on individuals leaving the men's sanitary facilities). However, the number of responses from women (26 in total)

⁴ It was the D.Event (an international conference on the theme of "Innovating with empathy: how to disseminate design thinking in an organisation"), organised by the D.School at Ecole des Ponts, which had taken part in the Azuris project.

showed a shared interest in the subject. Several interesting results emerged from the survey.

- With regard to the use of dry urinals, it should be noted that more than half of the men who had used them did not even notice that they were dry urinals. The vast majority of men who had used the urinals were satisfied: this comment applies equally to dry urinals and conventional urinals, which they praised for their practicality, their speed of use and, to a lesser extent, their interest in saving water. Among the reasons for dissatisfaction expressed by less than 10% of users were: "residual odour", "a bit dirty" and "people pee on the floor", while the remaining 8% had no opinion on their use.
- Nearly three-quarters of respondents did not know what happened to their urine when it was discharged and, more generally, had little or no knowledge of the management of their excreta. This high proportion reflects the general public's lack of knowledge about the impact of excreta discharge into sewage systems in terms of wastewater treatment and pollution downstream of the aquatic environment. This ignorance can compromise the attitude and behaviour of users when it comes to using dry urinals.
- The use of urine for agricultural purposes is perceived as relevant, with more than 90 % of respondents expressing a favourable opinion. Some expressed doubts about the quality of the fertiliser produced, and several respondents questioned the need for prior treatment.
- As for the prospect of consuming products grown using urine, this was also very well accepted, but was accompanied by concerns about the sanitary quality of urine-based fertilisers and demands that the products must be properly cleaned before consumption.

To sum up, this initial survey showed above all the importance of communicating strongly with the general public about source separation of excreta so that they can grasp the associated issues, both in terms of protecting the aquatic environment and the benefits in agricultural terms. It also showed that the dry urinal was an effective and already well-accepted device for implementing this practice in buildings open to the public.

3.1.2 The Garorock survey

The survey concerns the use of a prototype of a source-separating toilet deployed during a rock music festival on an open-air site located in a town in south-west France. The festival took place at the end of June 2019.

Context and objectives of the survey

The survey was carried out as part of the ANR-Design research project⁵. Involving various research laboratories and private partners, this project, which ran from 2018 to 2020, aimed to evaluate innovative scenarios for separating wastewater at source and reusing it, seeking to identify the benefits and constraints in environmental, technological, economic, sociological and urban planning terms.

A prototype of vacuum-separating toilets (using around 1 litre of water per flush) was developed with JP Coste, the project's industrial partner. These toilets have been specially designed to separate urine from faeces, passing them through separate networks to recover the fertilising elements they contain and to treat urine more effectively (in particular to eliminate micropollutants, antibiotics, etc.).

During the Garorock 2019 festival held in Marmande⁶ at the end of June, two examples of these toilets were installed in the Loge Entreprises and VIP area, with the idea of analysing both how they worked under heavy crowds and the experience of festival-goers who chose to use them. A poster and a video explaining the principle of the toilets were displayed near the booths and an instruction diagram for users was placed inside the booths themselves (Figure 3). A closed questionnaire was drawn up by the OCAP team. The interviewers, responsible for filling it in with the people interviewed during the festival, had been trained beforehand by the OCAP team. During the festival, the interviewers were stationed at the exit of the corresponding cubicles.

⁵ For more details on the project as a whole, see the web pages hosted by the TBI laboratory, coordinator of the project: <https://www.toulouse-biotechnology-institute.fr/projets/design/>

⁶ Marmande is located in south-west France, around 50 km from Bordeaux. Garorock has been held here for more than 20 years and has a national reach. So the scope of the survey is also national.

Figure 2: Survey at the toilet entrance and instructions inside

The questionnaire submitted to the respondents consisted of two parts: the first, comprising seven questions, regarding their experience of using the toilet model and their knowledge of alternative toilets to the conventional flush model; the second aimed to characterise their socio-economic profile and their environmental sensitivity, assessed by means of an "eco-gesture score"⁷.

Main findings

In all, over 140 questionnaires were collected at the event. The sample has a number of discrepancies compared with the demographic distribution of the French population: it is concentrated around the working population, with an over-representation of young people (which can be explained by the nature of the event, a rock festival) and it includes an over-representation of women (twice as many female respondents). However, this does not prevent us from drawing some interesting conclusions, not only about the model tested, but also about the knowledge and perception of source-separating toilets.

- The system was not avoided (festival-goers could choose to go to conventional toilets), and they took part in the questionnaire exercise without showing too much reluctance: it was therefore fairly quick to gather the opinions of a significant number of festival-goers leaving the toilets.
- Few users had problems with the toilets (occasionally with the flushing), and the majority had a positive impression of them, finding them practical or simply seeing no difference from conventional toilets. It is true that, in this operation (unlike the survey presented in the next section), the toilets look a lot like "normal" toilets.

⁷ The questionnaire listed a series of eco-actions such as producing renewable energy, using rainwater, composting kitchen waste, limiting water consumption, etc.

Moreover, a fraction of the people questioned did not pay attention to the instructions for use, even though they managed to comply with them.

- One of the main criticisms of the model was that the instructions required the user to sit down. However, in the context of public toilets, as is the case here, many people are reluctant to do so for hygienic reasons. The body posture adopted refers to a recurring problem related to the hygiene of the public toilets than to this specific model.
- While the survey showed that participants had a fairly good knowledge and/or practice of the different types of toilets that are alternatives to conventional water-based toilets, such as vacuum toilets, Turkish toilets, dual-flow economy toilets and including dry toilets, only a minority (less than a fifth) had ever heard of separating toilets. It is worth noting that this knowledge is shared across all genders and age groups⁸.
- While the vast majority of respondents indicated that this type of toilet could be installed in various public places, there was a relative reluctance to consider this type of toilet in their own homes. This relative reluctance concerning the domestic context seems to increase slightly with age, particularly for people over their 40s⁹.
- Respondents' environmental awareness apparently has no influence on their toilet-using experience. This can be explained by the fact that these toilets look very similar and are just as easy to use as conventional toilets, so no particular convictions are required.

To sum up, the survey shows a positive assessment, i.e. a majority acceptance of the type of toilets proposed, opening the doors to large-scale applications of separating toilets, albeit with some reluctance to install them in the home.

3.1.3 The survey at Cité Fertile

The survey concerned a set of conveyor belt dry toilets installed on a transitional urban development project located on the outskirts of Paris, in the commune of Pantin. It took place on an evening in October 2023.

Context and objectives of the survey

The survey was carried out as part of a partnership research project involving LEESU, a major construction group and Gustave Eiffel University (see section 2.2). As part of this project, two sites were the subject of a detailed analysis of operating conditions of alternative toilets. In the course of this work, it became apparent that these two cases should

⁸ None of those aged 55 and over had heard of separate toilets, but due to the nature of the event, this age group was very under-represented, so no conclusion can be drawn on this point.

⁹ Once again, this last conclusion was reached without taking into account the 55 age group, which was under-represented.

be compared with other experiments underway in the Paris region, and in particular with the Cité Fertile, where several conveyor belt dry toilets have been in service for several years, allowing us to take a step back from these two cases. Given the high number of visitors to the site (up to 10,000 on some weekends), the researchers involved decided to carry out a survey of users.

The principle of the conveyor belt dry toilets was explained by visuals on posters located in the washbasins adjoining the toilets (Figure 4). Underneath the seat opening is a conveyor belt: urine flows down the front of the belt by gravity into the sewage system¹⁰, while, by activating the conveyor belt (the carpet) with a pedal, faeces and toilet paper are sent backwards to be stored in large bins in a room adjoining the cubicle: they are to be composted *in situ*.

Figure 3: Poster explaining the Cité Fertile's dry toilets (details)

The questionnaire consisted of 19 questions divided into five sections: the respondent's use of the Cité Fertile; his or her experience using the dry toilets installed on the site; his or her past experience with alternative toilets to flush toilets; his or her knowledge of sanitation and current issues; and a characterisation of his or her socio-economic profile. The questionnaire was administered by two researchers involved in the project during an evening in October 2023, on a date previously approved by the site manager.

Main findings

Nearly 20 responses were collected. In addition to the direct answers to the questions, the questionnaire served as a tool for initiating sometimes more in-depth discussions with certain people, giving this survey an additional, more qualitative value. A number of conclusions can be drawn from this survey.

¹⁰ There is in fact a sewage network to which it is possible to connect. However, this does not correspond to the optimal operating mode of the model, which is designed to allow urine to be stored and used for agricultural purposes.

- Dry toilets seem to be becoming increasingly accepted. In fact, most of the responses show a positive view, with respondents wanting dry toilets to become more widespread and raising the argument that it is not rational to use drinking water to flush excreta. A majority of those questioned had already had experience of dry toilets in different contexts (festivals, holidays, particularly at campsites, private homes, etc.). The survey confirms what was already mentioned in the Garorock survey in 2019 (dry toilets are known to the general public, with several well-known models in some cases), while at the same time reinforcing its scope, namely that dry toilets are no longer seen as an innovative, experimental or alternative device, but as environmentally-friendly and suitable for certain contexts.
- On the other hand, the basics of sanitation appear to be poorly understood, in particular what happens to excreta (faeces and urine) once the toilet has been flushed. While the first stage is well known ("it goes down the drain!"; "it goes into the network!"), what happens beyond the treated wastewater plant is less well known. While some people think that everything goes "straight into the sea" (water and sludge), and others wonder whether it goes straight back into the drinking water network, or whether it goes into a grey water sub-network so that it can be used for cleaning, the majority have no precise idea, particularly as regards to what happens to the solids.
- As a result, ecological sanitation is a little-known or even unknown concept: the definitions proposed by the people interviewed are often very far removed from the concept, with some mentioning aquaponic sanitation, energy-efficient sanitation, and so on.
- In the context of a public place, dry toilets can go unnoticed and be 'transparent' for the user, when the constraints associated with their use are not too great compared with those of 'normal toilets' (flush toilets). In this case, the toilet model includes a pedal that you simply press with your foot to make the waste disappear. In this sense, in the minds of a number of people interviewed, they are comparable to conventional toilets, with people associating this foot action with flushing. So much so that some people even mistook them for 'normal toilets'. This is a far cry from BLTs (biolitter toilets), where the user has to handle shavings and is visually confronted with the material in the bucket, which is likely to upset some people.
- While the survey shows that conveyor belt dry toilets are highly acceptable, there are a few contrasting opinions: a small number of users were bothered by the smell or by the material (wood) used to make up the toilet frame, which was considered to be dirty, in contrast to the white enamel bowls.

Overall, these toilets are well-received appreciated in a collective and festive context. For some users, these toilets are even a plus that enhances the value of the venue, demonstrating the environmental awareness of the managers. Ultimately, in such a context, as long as the facilities are well managed, they do not pose a problem for users.

3.1.4 Survey of future users of the Saint-Vincent de Paul district (Paris)

This latest survey has a different scope compared to the previous ones in several aspects: on the one hand, it focuses on the housing context, and on the other hand, it has a forward-looking aim, since the toilets (separative model operating with a reduced flush), although identified at the time of the survey, have not yet been installed.

Context and objectives of the survey

As part of the environmental objectives assigned to the Saint-Vincent de Paul eco-neighbourhood, on a former hospital site in the 14tharrondissement, the City of Paris has decided to implement an ambitious scheme for the separate collection of urine and its *on-site* conversion into fertiliser. This is the biggest operation of its kind in France. The City of Paris has entrusted the public development company Paris & Métropole Aménagement (P&MA) with overseeing the construction of the eco-neighbourhood. The OCAPI programme is supporting this operation through a research-action process involving the City of Paris, LEESU and Cerema. As part of this research-action, it seemed appropriate to carry out specific work with the already selected future residents of the district to prepare them as well as possible to take charge of the toilets in their homes.

The aims of the survey were: to gather the views of a panel of these future residents and their questions and comments about the Saint-Vincent de Paul urine collection and recovery project; to find out more about their current toilet practices in order to identify the issues involved in adapting these practices for the future proper use of the separate toilets in their homes.

The survey was carried out in 2024, with the support of the public development company P&MA. It was sent to 63 households in the form of an online questionnaire preceded by some background information. The questionnaire was structured into 5 sections (profile of the respondent; general knowledge and perception of the urine collection project at Saint-Vincent-de-Paul; current toilet practices; perception and questions about separate toilets in the home; information and support systems for residents) and included around twenty questions. At the same time as the survey, any future residents who wished to take part attended an awareness-raising evening on the subject organised in the 'project house'¹¹, where an example of a separating toilet was installed for demonstration purposes.

Main findings

The survey attracted 46 responses. The sample of respondents was slightly over-represented by women, managers and professionals, and the 35-49 and 50-64 age groups. These brackets (especially the latter) were less present in the populations surveyed in previous surveys. The survey revealed a number of interesting findings about current toilet practices

¹¹ The 'project house' is a remaining small building located at the heart of the neighborhood : this building is used for meetings related to the project (stakeholders of the projects, visitors, etc.).

- Source separation and recovery of urine is still a little-known issue, but is well perceived. Around a third of respondents had heard of urine reuse as a fertiliser before the launch of the SVDP project, mainly through the media, informal discussions or the Internet. But the subject seems to be of arousing interest: when it is presented, it is generally received positively.
- Information about toilets has been provided gradually and is unevenly distributed. While a very large majority of respondents (around 9/10) were aware of the presence of separate toilets in their future homes, some, particularly among social tenants, only learned about it late in the day. Information was mainly disseminated via meetings organised by the project promoters, from 2021 onwards (the year in which the collection project will be integrated into the development of the neighbourhood).
- Support for the project appears strong and is largely motivated by ecological convictions. 80% of those surveyed said they were in favour, and none were explicitly opposed. This support is based on ecological reasons such as: contribution to the circular economy, reduction of water pollution, alternative to chemical fertilisers. Respondents also appreciated the innovative nature of the project and the opportunity to take part in a useful experiment. However, some respondents expressed concerns, either waiting for concrete results or because they were sceptical about the actual involvement of all residents.
- The user experience of the toilet model was generally positive. Nearly half of the participants had the opportunity to test the model of separate toilet installed as a demonstration in the project house within the eco-district under construction. These toilets were judged to be similar to conventional models, easy to use and did not require any change in habits. This pilot scheme helped to dispel some initial misgivings and familiarise users with the model.
- The practices of the respondents in their current toilets show that they need to evolve to adapt to the requirements of the system. A number of points need to be borne in mind: almost half still use conventional chemical products, which are incompatible with source-separating toilets; some users also flush down their toilets materials or liquids that will not be compatible with downstream collection (vomit, food scraps, etc.). There is still a need for information and education on good practice.
- Urinating while seated does not pose any obvious problems for men. Contrary to popular belief, this instruction (recommended to optimise urine recovery) does not seem to be a major obstacle, as the majority of men surveyed said they already urinated sitting down, at least occasionally. However, a quarter of the men surveyed expressed discomfort with this constraint.
- The questionnaires reveal a demand for diversified and targeted support. More

than half the respondents would like further information on the use and maintenance of separate toilets. Their expectations cover both technical aspects (maintenance, products to use, how to deal with malfunctions) and the overall operation of the system. The most popular features are signage in the toilets and written support materials. SMS reminders, on the other hand, were considered intrusive by some residents.

- Respondents would like to see the separation project and the promotion of urine-derived fertilisers made more visible in concrete terms. Respondents showed a real interest in the collective and symbolic dimension of the project, and the majority were therefore in favour of complementary actions such as organising visits to the urine treatment unit or creating communal areas where these urine-derived fertilisers could be used. Some original proposals emerged, such as setting up a form of mentoring for new residents. Future residents not only accept the project: they want to understand what it means, play an active part in it and see the practical benefits in their environment.

In summary, the survey revealed a very positive reception for the urine collection project and a high level of ecological awareness among residents, with widespread acceptance of separate toilets. The results do, however, highlight a need for targeted support, particularly in terms of the products to be used, the permitted and prohibited uses, and the maintenance of the facilities. In this respect, workshops, videos, flyers and actions in the field (tests, visits, signage) seem to be effective levers that need to be strengthened.

3.1.5 General conclusions

Taken as a whole, the surveys carried out between 2016 and 2024 in a variety of contexts (festivals, public places, collective housing, university buildings) reveal a growing acceptance of separate toilets. Overall, users express satisfaction with the toilets, particularly when they resemble conventional models or are simple to use. Some constraints, such as the need to sit down or odour-related discomfort, were mentioned, but only marginally.

However, the majority of respondents did not know what happens to excreta after flushing or what ecological sanitation involves. This lack of knowledge hampers the adoption of separate systems, even though information, when it is provided, arouses considerable interest.

The idea of using urine as fertiliser is very favourably received, driven by environmental concerns. Respondents see it as an opportunity to help reduce pollution. However, this support is sometimes accompanied by questions about health and the quality of treatment.

In the residential sector, as at Saint-Vincent-de-Paul, future users are curious and generally favourable to the project, even if behavioural adjustments are to be expected: limiting the use of chemical products, better understanding of the gestures compatible with the

system. The experience of a prototype tested on site proved useful in reassuring and familiarising residents.

Finally, these surveys underline the importance of maintaining the facilities and/or mediating with the public. When devices are well maintained (in terms of cleanliness) and well serviced (in terms of functionality), they are well accepted. The future of these technologies will therefore depend as much on their technical performance as on their inclusion in an approach to raising awareness and supporting change. In this sense, the question of the acceptability of these alternative toilets to users is in fact linked to the issue of the upkeep and maintenance of devices, an activity that is often hidden, sometimes forgotten, but essential to their smooth operation (Denis and Pontille, 2022). This leads us to broaden the scope of the analysis to include an understanding of the practices of the actors in charge of this activity, which is the subject of the next section of this report.

3.2 Monitoring the operation of source-separating toilets in the public sector

This section looks at the conditions under which source-separating toilets remain in operation over time, whatever the type of model concerned. The surveys mentioned in the previous section have shown that these toilets are now well accepted in a number of contexts *as long as their working order and cleanliness are guaranteed*. However, this is not self-evident; it requires a whole range of actions, which vary depending on the model, but which are not carried out automatically. This leads to malfunctions and, in some cases, toilet closures.

This is true in all cases, including conventional wet toilets, although in this case the reasons for malfunction are more limited to the proper disposal of waste downstream of the toilet cubicle¹². In addition to the issue of cleaning, two types of technical problem are involved (sometimes combined): a leak in the cistern or a blockage in the bowl trap or in the horizontal pipe. In the case of separate toilets, the issues are sometimes different (for example, in the case of dry urinals, the issue of odours arises), but also more complex as it is not just a question of ensuring that excreta are properly disposed of, but also of ensuring that the materials evacuated and/or stored are suitable for future recovery (with or without specific treatment, which may or may not be local). This calls for a wide range of skills, which vary from case to case.

However, with the exception of individual housing, where the proper functioning and cleanliness of toilets is usually the responsibility of the occupant (tenant or owner), these actions are carried out by third parties. Observing cases where separate toilets are heavily used reveals the practical actions and skills required, but also the challenges faced by the people in charge of these upkeep and maintenance activities. This section provides information on this subject through an analysis of a number of systems monitored or studied

¹² Strictly speaking, a distinction should be made between water toilets connected to the public sewerage system and toilets using on-site sanitation, where additional problems may arise with the "all-water" tank, the treatment and the downstream dispersal system. We will not go into these details here, as they differ from the case of separate toilets, whatever the type considered.

by the OCAPI team as part of a research project into the management of dry toilets in places accessible to the public, with a particular focus on operations involving transitional urban planning (Soyer, Legrand and de Gouvello, 2025).

3.2.1 Overview of the sites studied

The research project entitled "Dry toilets in semi-public spaces" was carried out between mid-2021 and early 2023. Its aim was to study dry toilets (or other alternative toilets) in semi-public areas. Four sites were analysed as part of this research, two main sites and two complementary sites.

Main site 1. Sud-Fleuri: alternative toilets in a future eco-neighbourhood

The first field of research is part of an existing partnership between the I-Site Future, a "scientific and institutional project on the city of tomorrow" run by the Université Gustave Eiffel (UGE)¹³, and a major construction company. To coincide with the construction of an eco-neighbourhood to the south of Paris (called Sud-Fleuri in the rest of this report¹⁴), I-site Future launched a call for experimental ideas in 2018, focusing in particular on water management. Two researchers (Bernard de Gouvello and Marine Legrand) drew up a proposal on the role of water and nutrients in the building, based on sanitary installations. This project was selected and was confirmed in a partnership agreement in 2019. The plan was to install alternative toilets in a building temporarily occupied during the construction phase. In practical terms, this involved a dry urinal for women and a toilet flushed with rainwater collected on the roof of the building (Figure 5,6). The urine is then to be recycled for the surrounding planting, in consultation with the landscaper in charge of Sud-Fleuri. However, the project took a long time to implement, with the vicissitudes of the overall site leading to several reconfigurations, including the final location of the facility in a temporarily open restaurant. The initial roadmap was difficult to keep up, and the ambitions for the demonstrator were revised downwards.

¹³ <https://www.descartes-devinnov.com/le-pole-dexcellence-ville-durable/i-site-future/> (consultation date: 12 July 2025).

¹⁴ For reasons of confidentiality with regard to the industrial partner, the latter is not mentioned and the name of the eco-neighborhood has been changed.

Figure 4: Women's dry urinal installed in the Sud-Fleury Eco-district

The trial ran from April 2021 (when construction of the system began) to March 2023, when it was decommissioned. The survey documents the experiences of all those involved in the project: the project manager from the construction company, the designer who conceived the device, the restaurant staff in charge of the toilets and the researchers behind the experiment.

Main plot 2. Plot Y: dry toilets on a university campus

The second plot also emerged from the Future I-Site, in 2020. It involved participating in the development of a plot of land on the Descartes Campus, known as "Parcelle Y", in the commune of Champs-sur-Marne. The first discussions date back to 2017. The initial aim was to pedestrianise the area and install small outdoor facilities to make it attractive to students. The UGE also wanted to make it a showcase for the "sustainable campus". The development is taking a long time to materialise, due to the diversity of the players involved and the many issues at stake. In 2020, the area undergoing a major overhaul, with new buildings springing up everywhere and a Grand Paris train station nearing completion. The land belongs to the EPA Marne, which is in charge of the overall plan, but the roads are managed by the conurbation. The local council gives its opinion on the issues affecting local residents. There were lively discussions about maintaining parking spaces, potential night-time nuisance, the sale of alcohol to students, etc. These issues will be decisive for the future of the experiment.

It was decided to develop the site in stages, starting with the installation of a restaurant-buvette, located in a container on Boulevard Descartes. Opposite the container, a wooden platform will be built for customers, which will be accessible outside the opening hours of the snack bar. In 2018, a UGE project manager, aware of the OCAP programme, suggested that the researchers set up an experiment to manage the flow of water and nutrients on campus. The same pair, who had been involved with Sud-Fleuri, renewed their collaboration with a similar idea: to combine innovative rainwater management with urine

management, by proposing a cubicle equipped with a separate dry toilet, a dry urinal and a rainwater recovery tank drained onto the roof (Figure 6).

Figure 5: Toilet cubicle and refreshment area on plot Y

The entire system was implemented in accordance with the initial specifications. However, the experiment came to a premature end with the unexpected closure of the refreshment bar-restaurant in January 2023, after 16 months of operation. The analysis considered the experiences of all the stakeholders directly concerned by the scheme: the UGE project manager, the refreshment bar manager, the designer of the booth, the pair of researchers and the users of the site.

La Cité Fertile: a complementary and more sustainable site on the outskirts of Paris

La Cité Fertile, created and managed by Sinny&Ooko¹⁵, is a third-party space dedicated to the challenges of the sustainable city, part of a transitional urban planning project by SNCF Immobilier. It occupies the space of the former goods station until the construction of the future Pantin eco- neighbourhood¹⁶. The site includes a bar-restaurant, a greenhouse, recreational areas for children and a range of activities (see photo *below*). It also offers several rooms for hire for events, is frequently privatised and can accommodate more than 10,000 people at weekends. Since the beginning of 2019, the Cité Fertile has had nine separate dry toilets with conveyor belts: the urine goes into the network, and the faeces are stored and dehydrated in large adjoining tanks. In summer, a dry toilet cubicle with bio-controlled litter¹⁷ is also used as a back-up toilet.

¹⁵ Sinny&Ooko is a Social and Solidarity Economy company based in the Paris region and specialised in the creation and management of third places.

¹⁶ Initially scheduled to run until 2022, this occupation was extended, first until September 2024, then beyond: the site is still open today.

¹⁷ Classic dry toilet model, with wood shavings added each time the toilet is used.

Figure 6: Overview of the Cité Fertile from the site entrance

Unlike the two previous operations, which were eventually discontinued, the dry toilets installed at the Cité Fertile were still in working order at the end of the research project (2023¹⁸). It is for this reason that this fieldwork complements the first two, providing an insight into certain aspects of the process of sustaining operations to install separate toilets.

3.2.2 Conditions for the sustainability of separate toilet systems

A comparative method has been put in place to monitor the trials over a period of 14 months, between June 2021 and July 2022. When the survey began, the toilets had been operational on the sites for several months. The objectives include documenting the appropriation of the system over time, reporting on the experience of the various stakeholders, understanding the problems encountered and their resolution, and assessing the role played by the implementation context. Particular attention was paid to housekeeping, upkeep and maintenance routines, which are crucial to the longevity of these objects. The analysis is based mainly on interviews with the people involved in managing the toilets in each operation, as well as several field visits at different points in the life of the experiments.

The analysis of the sites mentioned above confirms the initial intuition of the research regarding the crucial nature of upkeep and maintenance to ensure that dry toilets function properly over the long term, particularly when they are installed in transitional urban contexts. Far from being a purely technical matter, upkeep and maintenance involve organisational, institutional and socio-cultural dimensions. Research has highlighted a number of major issues relating to these three dimensions.

¹⁸ Apparently, these toilets are still functioning in 2025.

Organisational dimension

- The viability of dry toilets depends on their daily upkeep and regular maintenance. Dry toilets need to be carefully monitored, which means cleaning them daily (or even several times a day, as at Cité Fertile, where there is a large public), but also emptying the tanks regularly, monitoring any malfunctions (and taking rapid corrective action when a malfunction is found), and other operations that require an understanding of how they work and therefore specific skills. At Sud-Fleuri, a failure to maintain the female urinal quickly gave rise to odours that could not be corrected by cleaning operations (the source of the problem being downstream of the urinal itself), which discredited the system and contributed to its rejection. At La Cité Fertile, the people in charge of the toilets, who were away for part of the weekend, often had to empty and adjust the toilets on their return to make them operational, even though they had been cleaned several times during the weekend.
- The long-term survival of the systems installed depends on the involvement of the site managers. The dry toilets will only work in the long term if someone on site takes responsibility for them, either as their main activity or in addition to it. At the Cité Fertile, for example, site employees have been specifically mobilised to ensure the day-to-day management of the toilets: monitoring the tanks, cleaning, educational displays. At Parcelle Y, the refreshment bar manager is in charge. At Sud-Fleuri, on the other hand, the absence of a clearly designated local technical adviser has led to the gradual deterioration of the facilities.
- A DIY culture is an essential asset, especially for maintenance activities. Dry toilets often require simple but frequent material adjustments: repairing a pipe, adjusting a tank, improving ventilation. This presupposes that the people in charge have a degree of technical autonomy and a spirit of resourcefulness. At La Cité Fertile, the necessary adjustments (such as repairing a toilet's conveyor belt or adapting a traditional urinal) are carried out directly by the employees dedicated to this task. On plot Y, the experience acquired in previous humanitarian projects (including toilet management) by the refreshment stall manager gives him a skill and a spirit of initiative that enables him to solve several problems during the period when the toilets are in operation.

Institutional dimension

- The management of the toilets (and therefore their upkeep and maintenance) is weakened by the lack of clarity regarding the respective responsibilities of the players involved in setting them up. These systems fall outside the traditional regulatory and contractual frameworks, making their status ambiguous. This vagueness makes it difficult to identify who is responsible for maintenance. At Cité Fertile, the repeated tensions between the site manager and the service provider called in to maintain them just after they were set up revealed the absence of a clear contractual framework, which compromised the stability of the system over time: this situation was resolved by internalising the maintenance mission into the

activities of Cité Fertile staff. At Sud-Fleuri, the question of how to maintain the system remained an unresolved issue in the partnership between the researchers and the operational staff in charge of building the eco-neighbourhood: the public works company, despite owning the system, considered that this was the responsibility of the scientists who had proposed the experiment, while the latter felt that this issue should at least be the subject of dialogue and co-construction between the partners.

- The transitional urban planning context in which the operations analysed are located, while encouraging the introduction of innovative solutions (including separate toilets), is proving problematic in terms of the issue of their sustainability. The facilities are often perceived as temporary, which undermines the human and financial investment required for rigorous maintenance. On the campus hosting the toilets separating plot Y, the initial enthusiasm has waned with the loss of a long-term perspective. This gradual disengagement contributed to the partial abandonment of the dry toilets, illustrating the structural limits of the transitional framework.
- Because of their "low-tech" technology, dry toilets conflict with the prevailing standards, which are mainly designed for "high-tech" equipment. They fall outside the scope of traditional sanitation regulations, which hinders their recognition and logistical support. On plot Y, the refreshment outlet manager came up against a lack of clear procedures from the university campus management and had to forge his own maintenance procedure with his employees.

Socio-cultural dimension

- The correct use of dry toilets depends on users understanding what to do. Without clear information and mediation, inappropriate use can quickly damage the facilities. At Sud-Fleuri, the lack of visible instructions led to erroneous practices, while at Cité Fertile, the presence of explanatory signs and a well-informed team made it easier for people to adhere to and therefore maintain the facilities.
- The way toilets are kept clean and in good working order has a strong influence on how users perceive them. A well-maintained facility inspires confidence and support, whereas a dirty or poorly managed facility provokes rejection and disinterest. At Sud-Fleuri, negative feedback from visitors was directly linked to the visible deterioration of the facilities. At La Cité Fertile, on the other hand, the attention paid to aesthetics, hygiene and reception resulted in public recognition of the facility, reinforcing its legitimacy as a credible alternative.
- Lastly, maintenance can become an opportunity for learning, enabling the acquisition of specific skills and the enhancement of professions that are all too often invisible. This is particularly obvious in the case of Cité Fertile, where the employees in charge of maintenance, through the experience they have accumulated (intense in the context of the high number of visitors to the site), consider themselves to be

experts and express a certain pride in their work.

In conclusion, the upkeep and maintenance of dry toilets cannot be seen as a secondary issue. These activities are a cross-cutting issue and a fundamental condition for the sustainability and social acceptability of the systems. Their successful implementation requires practical skills, local roots and a flexible institutional framework, a collective commitment on the part of the players involved, and active educational work with users. Without this, despite their ecological potential and their relevance to a sustainable urban transition, the projects undertaken remain precarious.

4 The Azuris demonstrator

This section looks at the transformation of a modest experimental source separation system, created pragmatically and managed by researchers in the OCAPI programme at the Ecole des Ponts, into a large-scale demonstrator on the subject, designed to be integrated into the Ecole's asset management system.

4.1 Antecedents: experimentation within the Azuris project

Right from the inception of the OCAPI programme in 2015, phase 1 of which coincided with the thesis being carried out by Fabien Esculier, who is also in charge of the programme, the idea of having a device on site to show urine collection was born. This idea was formalised into the Azuris project.

4.2 The Azuris project

The researchers involved considered what form a light urine collection device could take at the Ecole des Ponts. With this in mind, they carried out a quick analysis of the existing toilet blocks in the various buildings on the site. It emerged that the Coriolis building (see photo and cross-section below) had favourable technical characteristics, making it possible to install a urine collection system without having to carry out too much work.

Figure 7: View and cross-section of the Coriolis building at Ecole des Ponts

Delivered in 2013, this building was built in accordance with a High Environmental Quality (HEQ) approach, including low energy consumption targets, in particular through the production of energy using solar panels on the roof, and a low drinking water consumption approach, through the use of rainwater from the roofs to flush the toilets and the installation of dry urinals in all the male toilets. The latter operate with a special siphon system to ensure watertightness and prevent odours from rising. One of these urinals is located on the ground floor of the building and urine is drained via a vertical pipe that is directly accessible from the ceiling of the car park below. It therefore seemed technically feasible to collect urine from this urinal. The Coriolis building also offered a favourable setting, thanks to the support of the D.School Paris team¹⁹, which had offices there: it showed an interest in the project and was willing to support it.

It was decided to include the implementation of a collection and storage system within the Coriolis building as part of a more global project created for the occasion: the AZURIS project (Valoriser l'AZote de l'URine de Coriolis). Its aim was to set up a collection system and a urine recovery chain, as well as to instrument the system in order to carry out an assessment of the effectiveness of the recovery of urine components.

The project began in spring 2016 with an M2-level student internship (Smaïl, 2016). Several actions were then carried out.

- A characterisation study of fresh and stored urine with a view to its recovery was carried out in order to analyse the effectiveness of urine treatment by storage. A system for collecting urine samples was defined and implemented near the men's urinal on the ground floor of the Coriolis building: users visiting these toilets were invited, if they wished, to fill in a sign-in sheet, take a bottle provided on the site and, after filling it with urine, place it in a refrigerator set up for this purpose. Over 70 samples were collected. The following parameters were analysed: total nitrogen content; phosphate, sulphate and chloride concentrations; pH; conductivity and mass.
- A tank for recovering urine from the dry urinal on the ground floor of the Coriolis building at the Ecole des Ponts was installed in the underground car park (details of the installation below).
- Research into agricultural outlets in the region has been carried out: avenues have been explored with a view to developing a local system for recovering urine as a resource.

This initial work made it possible to specify the characteristics expected of urine collected in the workplace, as well as the optimum collection methods. The results were encouraging and suggest that, simply by storing the urine, it will be highly effective in recovering nutrients. The operation also helped to raise awareness at the school of urine separation at source and its potential for use as a fertiliser, a subject that was largely unknown locally at the time.

¹⁹ <https://ecoledesponts.fr/dschool-paris>.

4.2.1 The experimental system set up by the researchers

Obtaining authorisation

Prior to setting up the facility, contact was made with the ENPC's Service des Affaires Immobilières et des Moyens Généraux (SAIMG) and a site visit was made: the OCAPi team was asked to provide a protocol describing the planned facility. Following these exchanges, a letter was finally sent to the General Secretary of the School in February 2016, co-signed by the Director of LEESU and the Head of the D.School, a stakeholder in the AZURIS project. The letter requested authorisation to: carry out the limited but necessary plumbing work to connect the urinal and the storage area; and to use the basement parking space next to the urinal to install the tank and all the equipment needed for the experiment. This authorisation was granted and constitutes the first official commitment by the School's administration to host a dedicated source separation facility on its premises.

The installation was carried out during the course of April 2016: the OCAPi team prepared the equipment in advance and a professional plumber was called in to carry it out.

Description of the installation

The general principle of the installation is to allow urine from the urinal on the ground floor of the Coriolis building to be diverted into a dedicated storage tank located in the building's underground car park. This diversion is achieved by installing a three-way valve on the drainage pipe coming from the urinal at the level of its exit from the ceiling of the car park.

The three-way valve is installed in place of the original single valve: depending on the position chosen, it allows urine from the urinal to be directed either towards the storage tank, via a pipe connecting the latter to the valve, or towards the sewerage system, using the original downstream pipe (Figure 9). The pipework to and from the storage tank was installed in line with the recommendations in force at the time, summarised in France by Samuel Lanoe (Lanoe, 2009), namely: horizontal pipes should have a slope of at least 1% (to avoid the formation of struvite associated with too slow a flow)²⁰; the system should not be ventilated (to avoid nitrogen losses); the tank should be filled from the bottom (to limit the exchange surface between the air and the urine), etc.

²⁰ In order to maximise run-off, the location of the tank allowed for an 8% slope.

Figure 8: Sheet of photos showing the dry urinal, the three-way valve and the storage tank

The storage tank is made of HDPE and is designed to collect rainwater. It holds 340 litres and measures 141 cm high and 64.5 cm wide (see photo above). Its size was calculated on the basis of an estimate of user frequency obtained by the Paris D.school, which counted almost 450 visits to these toilets in 3 weeks during October 2015. The tank was raised with cinder blocks to allow 20-litre drums to be filled.

A lockable office-type metal cupboard has been installed in the allocated parking space. It stores all the equipment needed to operate the installation correctly: a handle for changing the position of the three-way valve, a technical diagram, an operating logbook listing all the operations carried out, in particular emptying the tank, the equipment needed to carry out these emptying operations (cans, gloves and masks, a marker to indicate the date on the cans, etc.). The site also contains a schematic diagram and information panels for use during specific events.

Managing the installation

The system's operating mode has gradually stabilised.

By default, the system does not recover urine, the three-way valve sends it directly to the sewage system. If urine is needed for a given experiment²¹, a campaign is launched, the three-way valve is manipulated and the urine is directed to storage. The filling level of the tank is regularly checked and when it exceeds a certain threshold, the cans are filled, using a protocol designed to protect the operator carrying out the manipulation. The operator takes the key to the cupboard from a hiding place, opens it and takes a pair of gloves, overalls, a short flexible hose to connect to the tap, a canister to be filled and a sponge with a hole in it to allow the hose to pass into the canister, while avoiding the release of nitrogen. Once the canister(s) have been filled, they are labelled with the day's date, before being stored on a shelf in the cupboard; the operation is recorded in an *ad hoc* notebook, also kept in the cupboard. Once the equipment has been rinsed with water, the cupboard is locked again.

This method of operation is well suited to researchers, but it does have a number of limitations. Firstly, the system has no level sensor of overflow to the sewage system, so during a given campaign it is essential to check the level in the tank frequently to avoid urine spilling into the car park²². Secondly, it is only operated by trained researchers involved in the programme, which limits its period of use, which is very intermittent. In addition, it can only produce one quality of urine-fertiliser, i.e. raw urine that can be used after 6 months' storage. Finally, although the car park has restricted access, it is not located in a dedicated technical room.

Initial thoughts on developing the system

Over the course of the system's operation, prior to the P2Green project, two projects initiated discussions on the possibilities for developing the experimental system and its management.

In 2019, as part of a research internship supervised by Fabien Esculier, a study was conducted into the feasibility of extending urine collection in the building, with a view to turning it into a larger-scale demonstrator (Dargentolle, 2019). This study showed that there were many obstacles to the deployment of such a project: the technical feasibility of collecting urine in an existing building, the number of stakeholders with different interests involved, user acceptability, and economic, health, regulatory issues, to name a few. It also proposed several scenarios - of increasingly complex technical feasibility - for extending urine

²¹ The urine is used for various types of tests: production of struvite in the laboratory; field tests, in situ on potted plants or on a cultivation plot made available by the manager of the community garden run by the school's students, etc.

²² This incident has indeed occurred several times: this is why the "valve closed" position was adopted as the default situation.

collection in the building, taking into account the willingness of the various stakeholders to get involved in the project.

In 2020, a group of 5 students on placement at the Paris D.School, co-supervised by Bernard de Gouvello and Alessandro Arbarotti from the OCAPI programme, focused more specifically on the issue of transferring operations to the School's managers (Benedetti C., Benmeziani A., Paré C. and Tan W., 2020), by asking the question: how can the Azuris system be made sustainable and manageable by non-specialists? The students analysed the system management practices adopted by the researchers and proposed ways of formalising and developing these practices in order to simplify them, guarantee their safety and make it easier to transfer this management to the School's logistics teams.

Although these last two initiatives did not lead to any concrete changes, they did provide useful lessons for the project to come.

4.3 Intentions and principles of the AZURIS demonstrator project

4.3.1 The P2Green project: an opportunity to develop the demonstrator

The P2Green project is an opportunity to relaunch the process of transforming the experimental system. As part of the OCAPI program's contribution to the project, through task 3.3 (and more specifically the analysis of stakeholders in charge of buildings housing separate toilets), funding is provided to improve the existing system by including new types of separation devices, not yet studied in France.

The P2Green project, with the presence of specialists in the field in various European countries, also provides a suitable framework for discussion (as mentioned in section 3.3. of this report).

A designer (Louise Raguét) was commissioned to create the demonstrator. As an active member of the OCAPI programme, Louise Raguét has been familiar for many years with the theme of separation at source, a subject to which she devoted part of her final diploma from the ENSCI (École Nationale Supérieure de Création Industrielle) obtained in 2019 by developing a female urinal, named "Marcelle"²³. She had the opportunity to use this urinal on a number of projects, including the Grands Voisins operation, which took place on the site of the Saint-Vincent-de-Paul eco- neighbourhood.

Post-doctoral work is also planned in connection with this demonstrator. Supervised by Bernard de Gouvello and Marine Legrand, two researchers who have been involved in the OCAPI programme since its inception, this post-doctoral work will look at the conditions for the sustainability of innovative excreta source separation systems: in this context, the implementation of the Coriolis building demonstrator will be put into perspective with other operations that have already been completed on projects in the Paris region.

²³ See <https://urinoirmarcelle.fr/>.

4.3.2 The proposed principles

To begin with, an analysis was carried out of how the current system was working, and interviews were also conducted with several administrative managers at the Ecole des Ponts in order to understand the constraints associated with the building and its management. This work was carried out by Louise Raguet, with the participation of Fabien Esculier, and Corentin Eschenbrenner, post-doc fellow on the Freezepee project²⁴, whose treatment process is intended to be incorporated into the demonstrator.

This work has made it possible to specify the principles and objectives assigned to the new demonstrator, namely:

- setting up an operational recovery chain, which will involve developing partnership(s) with one or more farms in the region and simplified logistics;
- significantly increase the quantity of urine collected (currently limited by the connection of a single urinal, which is not even permanent);
- install a variety of urine-collection systems: urine-diverting toilets, waterless urinals for women or both sexes, etc;
- focus exclusively on urine collection solutions;
- implement a number of urine treatments, designed with a conservative approach.

4.3.3 Debating the project

The principles and objectives outlined above were discussed in two forums: within the OCAPi programme, and during a workshop organised as part of the P2Green project.

Internal discussion within the OCAPi programme

A presentation was made on the 3rd of October 2024 at an internal meeting of the OCAPi programme to gather the opinions and comments of programme members on the principles envisaged. While most of the objectives were approved by those present, some felt that the decision to leave out faeces was unfortunate. Following this discussion, a number of ideas were put forward to see how dry toilets could be integrated into the Coriolis demonstrator project. One idea that came to light was to move the Y batch cabin, which had been closed for more than a year, back to the Ecole des Ponts site near the Coriolis building²⁵.

²⁴ Initiated in 2014, the aim of the FreezePee project (<https://www.leesu.fr/ocapi/freezepee-evaluation-dun-procede-novateur-de-cryoconcentration/>) is to draw up a new inventory of existing and emerging channels for recovering urine in agriculture and to evaluate them. As part of this project, experiments will be carried out on recent advances in the concentration of nutrients by freezing, a treatment process that will be incorporated into the demonstrator.

²⁵ Steps have been taken to this end with the relevant authorities at the Université Gustave Eiffel. The principle has been accepted, the cost of moving the tank has also been validated and discussions are underway to determine the most appropriate location.

The P2 Green workshop (Florence meeting)

On the first day of the 4th consortium meeting of the P2GreenN project, held from 13 to 15 November 2024 in Florence, the OCAPI team proposed a workshop to the consortium members present. Led by Louise Raguet and Bernard de Gouvello, the aim of the workshop was to reflect collectively on the transformation of the Azuris system in the Coriolis building into a demonstrator of excretate source separation. After an initial presentation of the principles and ideas formulated within OCAPI for this demonstrator, two groups were formed to deal with three themes: the project's salient points, strengths and risks (groups 1 and 2), and the research questions that the demonstrator could enable to be explored in greater depth (group 3). Each group worked freely and creatively using a post-its session.

The project as presented offers a number of advantages. It allows different technologies to be experimented with and demonstrated in terms of both collection and processing, while also serving as an educational and communication tool via events, dissemination documents and a building designed as a "living lab". It also relies on the visual enhancement of results and the involvement of users in the co-design process.

However, a number of risks have been identified. Problems with odour, maintenance, tank monitoring or the compatibility of cleaning products could compromise the user experience. Other issues concern regulations on the agricultural use of urine, the mismatch between the agricultural and university seasons, and temperature variations. To remedy these problems, participants suggested making a rigorous choice of suppliers, installing a large number of sensors, defining appropriate cleaning protocols and involving the technical teams in charge of the building.

Numerous avenues of research were raised. From a sociological point of view, it was suggested that we should study changes in behaviour and perceptions over time, paying particular attention to gender differences and the user experience. From an economic point of view, the importance of defining a rigorous method capable of clarifying the additional costs specific to experimental facilities and estimating the resulting savings, particularly in energy, was stressed. From a technical point of view, emphasis was placed on the importance of defining cleaning and maintenance procedures for the systems, and developing a rigorous method for sizing them. It was pointed out that, in terms of quality, the differentiated collection of urine (according to gender, type of toilet or eating habits) could help to produce a standardised fertiliser. Finally, studies on N₂ and N₂O emissions according to the treatments used should be considered to better assess environmental impacts.

4.4 Description of the proposed project

On the basis of the discussions held and suggestions made, the project has been amended. However, beyond this initial revision, economic constraints have led us to opt for a phasing and prioritisation of the work to be carried out.

4.4.1 Constraints and prioritisation in defining the project

While the initial ambition was to aim for the widespread installation of separate toilets and dry urinals connected to a dedicated network, the scope has been reduced several times.

- Equipping the south wing seemed much more technically complicated: this point was highlighted in 2019 in the assignment then entrusted to Lise Dargentolle (Dargentolle, 2019). This is why, at the start of the project, it was decided to limit the project to equipping the toilets in the north wing, which are already more or less connected with the future urine collection and treatment room.
- However, for economic reasons, the scope of the project had to be scaled back: We initially focused our requests for quotes on equipping only the ground floor toilets, in order to reserve a substantial portion of the budget for constructing a technical room in the building's basement—designed to house the treatment devices and meet the required standards. This option appeared to be a necessity in view of the desired eventual transfer of day-to-day management of the facility (currently carried out by the OCAP research team) to the Ecole des ponts asset manager and his associated teams.
- Finally, the initial plumbing and structural work estimates have required a reduction in the number of toilets to be equipped, in order to preserve the priority of constructing the urine treatment room in the car park starting in 2025. The medium-term goal remains to equip all ground floor toilets—ideally from 2026—with additional funding.

The work planned for the end of 2025 is therefore as follows:

- Installation of a urine collection and treatment room in the basement of the building, at car park level: construction of the walls, electrical equipment, ventilation and plumbing;
- Installation of a urine-diverting bowl and a waterless urinal for women in the ground-floor toilet on the women's side. The waterless urinal on the men's side will be retained and urine will also be collected from this urinal.

4.4.2 Description of the technical solutions chosen

The specifications for phase 1 of the project have been drawn up. The main elements are set out below.

Urine collection

Urine will be collected *via* the Laufen Save! separating toilet installed in the women's toilets (Figure 11), with diluted urine passing through a dedicated network, and via the existing men's urinal and the women's urinal installed in place of a conventional toilet, with raw urine passing through another network. Raw and diluted urine are kept separate until they reach the basement.

Figure 9: Photos and principle of the Save! model by Laufen

The waterless urinal for women will be installed in the sanitary facilities on the women's side, in a non- PRM cubicle (replacing the current toilet). The model chosen has not yet been decided, but there are several available on the market (Figure 12).

Figure 10: Examples of waterless urinals for women: left: Marcelle, right: Madame PEE

A waste bin and appropriate signage should be installed alongside the female urinal to help users become familiar with this "new" fixture. (Figure 13).

Figure 11: Examples of female urinal signage (source: Marcelle urinal)

The men's toilets already have a waterless male urinal with a membrane siphon. This urinal will be retained.

Equipment room and treatment systems

A schematic diagram of how the basement of the demonstrator will be organised is shown below (Figure 14). Four selected treatment systems will be installed:

1. *Nitrification by "Pitribon"*: this is a passive filter using vegetable carbon. This low-tech system was developed by Aneco in Switzerland²⁶. It has the advantage of being very easy to install and consuming very little energy (with only a lift pump and a small internal heater to keep the system at 20°C).
2. Activated carbon filter: for filtering micropollutants from urine, particularly pharmaceutical residues.
3. Concentration by freezing: this system was developed by the Rich Earth Institute²⁷. It concentrates urine using a freeze-thaw process. The development of the machine and analysis of the urinofertiliser produced will be carried out as part of the *Freeze-Pee* research project.
4. *Hygienisation by storage* (for 6 months): this treatment does not involve any special equipment, just a relatively large storage volume. This option will be chosen "by default" if it is necessary to simplify the treatment system, particularly for the building's technical teams.

²⁶ Aneco is a Swiss association made up of a dozen members involved in ecological remediation projects (cf. <https://an-eco.ch/>).

²⁷ The Rich Earth Institute is dedicated to research, education and technological innovation to advance the use of human waste as a resource. (see <https://richearthisstitute.org/>).

Figure 12: Diagram of principle of the organisation of the basement of the demonstrator

4.5 Conclusion

Setting up the demonstrator is proving to be a complex operation, and therefore slower than expected, for several reasons, mainly two intertwined. The first is that, from a technical point of view, it is more complicated to work on an existing building than on a new one where the design can take account of the presence of this specific equipment. Working on an existing building means looking for specific solutions, being inventive and working out technical compromises that are compatible with existing constraints. The second reason is that obtaining the support and authorisation of the various people involved in the project, who come from different departments within the School and beyond (for certain service providers), requires education and time, and generates delays. However, this whole process is a time for the project to mature and for the stakeholders' perception of the subject to evolve. It is a key phase in the demonstration initiative, with a view to involving ENPC departments in the day-to-day running of the facility once it is completed.

But this configuration is also what makes the present demonstrator so interesting. It provides an opportunity to provide detailed information on the delicate socio-technical process of transforming an existing “conventional” building into a building producing urine-fertilisers.

5 General conclusion

Dedicated to the conditions of acceptability for users of segregated toilets in different projects mainly located in the Ile-de-France region, this report has been structured into two main sections. The first section focused on user acceptability, based on a series of surveys conducted between 2016 and 2024 in a variety of contexts, including music festivals, university campuses, semi-public venues and residential eco-neighbourhoods. It included a detailed analysis of how maintenance and institutional support are organised to ensure the day-to-day and long-term sustainability of the devices, a crucial aspect of their acceptability to users. The second section presented the evolution of the Azuris demonstrator at École des Ponts, a pilot initiative that illustrates the challenges and opportunities of integrating ecological sanitation into an existing office building. Together, these sections offer a broad perspective on the issues of user acceptability of segregated toilets by combining field data, case studies and practical experiments.

In all the case studies and surveys, one major finding emerges: public acceptance of source-separated sanitation systems is generally positive when the technology is intuitive to use, clean and well maintained. When toilets resemble conventional models and are easy to use, users take to them and even tend to ignore the details that differentiate them. The notion of reusing urine as fertiliser is generally well received, with many participants seeing it as an innovative and environmentally friendly practice. However, this enthusiasm is potentially tempered by a lack of understanding of the wider sanitation system and technical constraints, particularly in the context of housing, such as the incompatibility of certain cleaning products with urine collection and treatment processes.

The role of maintenance, often overlooked, is essential to the success of these systems. Case studies of both successful and abandoned projects show that user satisfaction is directly linked to the visibility, consistency and quality of system maintenance. When maintenance is clearly structured and routinely carried out - as is the case at Cité Fertile - the user experience is enhanced, and long-term acceptance is guaranteed. In contrast, projects such as Sud-Fleuri and Parcelle Y were terminated prematurely due to unclear roles, institutional fragmentation and inadequate services. Maintenance must therefore be understood not just as a technical operation, but also as a central socio-institutional practice.

The development of the Azuris demonstrator illustrates this socio-technical interaction. While the renovation of an existing building introduced technical and logistical complexity, it also led to dialogue between the stakeholders. Delays caused by coordination problems and the need for internal advocacy are part of the process of maturing the project, which leaves time for cultural change and institutional learning. Setting up the demonstrator is not just a technical operation, but an awareness-raising and capacity-building tool designed to anchor the system in daily routines and responsibilities.

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